

ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF EXISTING CYBER-PHYSICAL SYSTEMS

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Abstract. *Cyber Physical System (CPS) - is an intelligent computerized system that uses controlled mechanisms and various algorithms to combine software and hardware components to ensure their functionality and show various methods and approaches. CPS are a development of embedded systems characterized by tight integration of common computing elements, such as microcomputing units or interconnected embedded systems through a communication network. In the context of CPS, a variety of intelligent devices, including sensors, actuators, machines, robots, etc., are interconnected to form an intelligent ecosystem capable of collecting data and initiating actions in the physical world. This connectivity has enormous potential for innovation in a variety of sectors such as aerospace, automotive, civil infrastructure, energy, healthcare, transportation, entertainment, home appliances, manufacturing and manufacturing. In the field of manufacturing, the CPS approach provides a holistic abstraction of the hardware components that make up the manufacturing system. This abstraction is crucial because it facilitates a model-based engineering approach to the configuration of entire manufacturing systems, leading to a significant reduction in the time to create, scale, and reconfigure manufacturing automation systems [1]. The resulting modular automation architecture is called "open automated manufacturing." Achieving this requires standard solutions for the*

communication infrastructure that connects the embedded systems that control the various production modules. Viable options include using industrial networking layer approaches such as PROFINET or using standard web technologies such as Services Oriented Architecture (SOA). In this article, we will consider the main types of existing cyber-physical systems and their applications, as well as describe the most important problems faced by systems that use CPS.

Keywords: *cyber-physical systems, CPS, digital systems, conceptual models, cybernetics.*

Review of existing cyber-physical systems. Cyber-physical systems (CPS) are those IT systems that are implemented in applications of the physical world. Sensors and actuators are already built into these systems. Advances in ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) lead to greater communication between the cyber world and the physical world, which in turn increases the interconnectedness of physical processes.

Cyber-physical systems (CPS) represent a new generation of embedded control systems capable of providing control and management of the physical environment. Many fields, such as energy, transportation, and healthcare, are increasingly favoring the use of CPS. It is important to note that the choice of a specific technology determines the relevance and importance of CPS. For example, a supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system used in critical infrastructure such as smart grids and industrial process control systems is an important example of CPS. Also of note is the use of wearable and implantable medical devices (IMDs) in the healthcare industry. Hence, given the variety of CPS applications, enumerating all their variations is a daunting task. Here we list four representative CPS programs, providing important details about each:

a) **Industrial Control Systems (ICS):** Industrial process control (ICS) infrastructure, including SCADA and distributed control systems, is a system that improves production control and efficiency while overseeing various industrial

sectors, such as nuclear power plants, water and sewage systems, and also irrigation systems. ICS uses various controllers, such as programmable logic controllers (PLCs), that have a variety of capabilities to achieve the desired results. Sensors and actuators are used to interact with the physical environment. This system uses both wireless and wired connections, depending on the environment. In addition, ICS can manage operations in a control center by connecting to computer systems.

b) Smart Grid Systems: Having successfully used power grids for decades, the smart grid represents the next level of power generation with enhanced functionality. Locally, this makes economic and environmental sense, allowing consumers to better control their energy consumption. Nationally, this improves emissions control, globally balances the load and saves energy.

c) Medical devices: Cybernetic and physical capabilities are used to create advanced medical devices to provide high-quality medical services. These devices are designed to serve patients by being implanted inside the body [2] or worn on an external surface. They are smart and have the ability to communicate wirelessly with other devices. This communication is provided by the software required to update and configure the devices. The wearable device is particularly useful for monitoring patient activity.

d) Smart transport: Smart transport means vehicles that are more environmentally friendly, more economical, safer and that provide greater convenience in use. These developments are made possible by network computers (electronic control units) which are responsible for monitoring and regulating various functions such as engine emission control, braking, entertainment and comfort functions. These technologies have become most important in the modern era to reduce traffic jams, accidents and other problems on the roads and in the regions.

Trends in medical cyber-physical systems. A Medical Cyber-Physical System (MCPS) represents advanced medical technology that uses advanced embedded systems and networking to monitor and manage the physical dynamics of patients. These technologies include proton therapy machines, electroanatomical

mapping and intervention, biocompatible and implantable devices, and robotic prosthetics. It is important to consider that improper use of these tools can significantly affect the patient's health. Ensuring the safety and accuracy of all interactions is a critical task, but it is complicated by their high complexity. Modeling and effectively reproducing the patient's physiological characteristics will be of great importance for the development and testing of medical CPS and individualized treatment plans. In the near future, hospitals will be able to use real-time modeling of the patient's body, which will open the possibility of using model clinical diagnostics and treatment planning without the need for supercomputers.

MCPS attracts the attention of many individuals who want to make their lives easier through the diagnosis or treatment of various diseases. However, the significant modernization of these devices creates new challenges in the field of software (and also opens up new opportunities for the scientific research community). The main trends in the development of medical devices can be summarized as follows:

a) As a result of the introduction of new technologies into the software of medical equipment, such as robotic surgery and proton therapy, new functional possibilities arise. These technologies are based on the principles of embedded systems. Robotic surgery, for example, needs to process high-resolution images and provide real-time tactile feedback. Treatment with proton therapy is one of the most technologically advanced methods, including a large number of medical devices. A major difficulty is that the proton beam must be carefully distributed to different locations for different patients, opening up opportunities for intervention in beam planning and delivery. Over the past decade, many researchers have investigated the safety of proton therapy devices, but most of their research is limited to individual devices and emergency shutdowns. Consequently, the analysis and evaluation of these large and complex systems is one of the main challenges facing the medical device manufacturers and industry.

b) In the modern era, medical devices increasingly use software and are equipped with network interfaces to provide high connectivity. These integrated medical devices enable the creation of a distributed network that must be properly designed and tested to perform specific functions or appear as patients (to treat diseases). They are used for patient monitoring and integration with electronic health records (EHR) to store patient data through local connection of individual devices for integrated patient monitoring or remote monitoring in telemedicine. In the current scenario, the capabilities of such medical devices are limited by the parameters and regulations set by device manufacturers and medical professionals. This leads to increased patient safety and the introduction of new treatment methods. The Plug-and-Play Medical Device Initiative (MD PnP) [3] offers an open standard framework for the secure and scalable connectivity of medical devices, contributing to improved patient safety and healthcare efficiency.

c) Due to the high costs of hospitalization, there is a growing interest in exploring alternative methods of care, such as home health care, telemedicine and sports monitoring. The use of mobile and home monitoring of important indicators and physical activity allows remote safety assessment at any time. In addition, various medical devices can measure parameters such as heart rate, breathing rate, blood sugar level, stress level and skin (patient/person) temperature. However, without real-time diagnostic capabilities, these devices operate in data storage and transfer mode. The use of closed-loop technology in physiology will allow clinical assessment of vital functions in real time and will require constant monitoring.

Discussion. For the physical environment to work effectively, it is necessary to monitor the behavior of physical processes and take measures that can affect their dynamics. It was for this purpose that the Cyber-Physical Communication System (CPS) was created. CPS consists of two main parts: a physical process and a cyber system that interact with each other. As the interoperability between them increases, the impact of cyber security threats on the physical system increases, making CPS security extremely important [4,5]. CPS has had many attacks stopped over the past

decade. For example, the Stuxnet worm attack in 2010 caused serious damage to Iran's nuclear facilities [6]. Some hackers tried to affect air traffic control systems in the United States. Carshark software allowed hackers to turn off a car's engine and even stop it remotely in 2010. There have also been cases where hackers interfered with the control system of Siemens factories with the help of viruses, worms or patches. In some cases, hackers have been able to break into medical devices implanted in people's bodies using wireless connections or Android apps. Many cyber-physical systems, such as digital power grids, intelligent transportation systems, medical systems, and defense systems, face various types of security flaws.

Future CPS will include not only physical, but also chemical and biological components, where information can be represented in different substances and forms. Multiscale informatics (MSI) will provide the ability to extract information from these components, as well as determine the ways of its distribution and integrate them physically, syntactically, semantically and operationally for more efficient operation. Although MSI is an important component of information theory, its use requires further research and effort. The complexity of technologies complicates the issue of security of new systems, but at the same time makes it extremely important. When designing complex systems, such as CPS or the Internet of Things, it is important to consider the large number of devices that cooperate and can change their structure [7]. It is also important to ensure that the system remains secure and reliable, even after the user has used it.

The role of ontologies in CPS. The term "ontology" comes from the ancient Greek words "ontos" meaning "being" and "logos" meaning "discourse". Over time, ontology acquired different meanings:

- Ontology serves as a formal, shared and explicit representation of concepts in a certain domain.

- In computer science, an ontology is a formal method of representing knowledge by defining a set of concepts within a domain. It uses a common vocabulary to formulate the types, properties, and relationships of these concepts.

- In the field of manufacturing systems, effective knowledge management faces challenges due to the variety of configurations that manufacturing systems can take. Consequently, the generalization of manufacturing systems design and management methods often hinders diverse application contexts. Numerous authors have addressed this problem, especially in recent years, thanks to advances in information technology tools, particularly the concept of object orientation (OO) and related technologies.

Since the 1990s, ontologies have been proposed to describe manufacturing systems, offering improved capabilities to address these challenges. In addition, when properly implemented in appropriate languages, ontologies facilitate the incorporation of such knowledge into software and automated systems.

An effective approach to understanding the impact of cyberattacks on physical systems involves modeling cyber-physical systems (CPS) using ontologies [8,9]. An ontology is a formal representation of knowledge that encompasses a set of concepts within a domain and the relationships between them. For such a representation, it is important to formally specify components such as individuals (object instances), classes, attributes, relationships, as well as constraints, rules, and axioms. Ontologies not only represent a common and reusable representation of knowledge, but also contribute to new understanding of a subject area.

They offer several advantages:

- Enable automated data justification.
- Provide the ability to represent data formats, including unstructured, semi-structured, or structured data, facilitating seamless data integration, concept and text analysis, and data-driven analytics.
- Support the addition of additional relationships, integration of multiple ontologies, and cross-domain concept mapping.

Conclusion. Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) are transforming various industries by tightly integrating computational and physical elements through advanced communication networks. The review highlights the transformative

potential of CPS in sectors such as industrial control, smart grids, healthcare, and transportation. These systems enhance efficiency, safety, and functionality, contributing significantly to technological advancements. Despite the vast benefits, CPS face significant challenges, particularly regarding security. The increasing complexity and connectivity of these systems make them susceptible to cyber threats, emphasizing the need for robust security measures. Future developments in CPS will likely incorporate chemical and biological components, adding layers of complexity and necessitating further research in multiscale informatics (MSI) to manage and secure these advanced systems effectively. The role of ontologies in CPS may help in improving system design and management. Ontologies facilitate better understanding, integration, and security of CPS by providing a formal representation of knowledge and relationships within a domain. In conclusion, CPS hold immense promise for enhancing various sectors. The ongoing research and development efforts in these areas are vital for realizing the full potential of CPS and ensuring their secure and efficient deployment in the future.

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